

Creative Magic Squares: Permutable Base-Power Digits Representations

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*This paper brings magic squares of orders 3 to 10 in terms of **permutable powers-bases digits**. It means that in a same numbers, there are same digits in powers and bases. In case of order 10 there are two possibilities are given. One as general normal magic squares and another as **block-bordered** magic square, with inner block as pandiagonal magic square of order 8. Previous works of similar kind is done with single digit [15] and single letter [16].*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA;

Instagram: @crazynumbers.

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1 Introduction

Let's consider the following procedure:

1.1 Procedure

Let us consider, $(a, b)^{(a,b)}$, where $a, b \in 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9$. Extending it for more number of digits, i.e., for 3, 4, 5, etc., we have a general procedure:

$$\begin{aligned} &(a, b)^{(a,b)}; \\ &(a, b, c)^{(a,b,c)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d)^{(a,b,c,d)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d, e)^{(a,b,c,d,e)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d, e, f)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d, e, f, g)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i)}; \\ &(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j)}. \end{aligned}$$

where, $a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, with no repetition of number in each case. Each line of (??) represents the length, for example, the first line is of length 2, second line is of length 3, etc. See below:

$(a, b)^{(a,b)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 2
$(a, b, c)^{(a,b,c)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 3
$(a, b, c, d)^{(a,b,c,d)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 4
$(a, b, c, d, e)^{(a,b,c,d,e)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 5
$(a, b, c, d, e, f)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 6
$(a, b, c, d, e, f, g)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 7
$(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 8
$(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 9
$(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j)}$	$\longrightarrow$	Length 10.

The procedure is for the digits 0 to 9, 1 to 9, etc. Few works of author in this direction can be seen in [1, 5, 6]. Below are few examples in both the possibilities i.e., from 0 and 1 onwards. In each case they are minimum possible:

$25 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$626 := 0^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$
$215 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 6^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$	$656 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$
$217 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 6^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$	$664 := 0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1$
$242 := 0^3 + 3^5 - 5^0$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$730 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$244 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^4$	$754 := 0^8 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 8^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2$
$256 := -0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4$	$767 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 8^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1$
$342 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$792 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$
$344 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 7^3$	$= -1^9 + 2^8 + 8^1 + 9^2$	$794 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$
$511 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^1$	$809 := 0^9 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 811 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
 853 &:= 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 855 &:= 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 867 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 898 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 &= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 900 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 &= -2^6 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 943 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 &= -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 \\
 970 &:= 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^0 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1 \\
 971 &:= 0^9 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^3 &= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
 972 &:= 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1
 \end{aligned}$$

For the complete list refer author's work [1, 4, 6]. Using all the digits from 0 to 9 are given in [2, 3, 4]. In Appendix 4, there is a list 0 to 1000 numbers written in two possibilities. One from 0 to 9 and another from 1 to 9.

The aim of this work is to write magic squares from orders 3 to 10 using the idea given in above examples. All the magic squares in the Section 2 are given in for the representations from 1 onwards. The readers can try it for second possibility, i.e., from 0 onwards.

2 Permutable Powers-Bases Digits Magic Squares

In recent works [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13], the author worked with **magic squares**. These works include **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic square from order 3 to 47. Summarized work on magic square can be seen in [14]. Below are basic magic squares of orders 3 to 10, and their representations in terms of single letters. Few exercises are also written. Similar kind of work for **single digit** and **single letter** can be seen in [15, 16].

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

Example 2. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 3 given in Example 1 is given by

			$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$
$1^7 + 7^1$	$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$
$1^2 + 2^1$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$1^6 + 6^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$
$1^3 + 3^1$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$
$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$

Exercise 1. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 3 in natural numbers:

			$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
$2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$

2.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 3. Let's consider a **pandigonal** magic square of order 4 given by

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

Example 4. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given in Example 3 is given by

		$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
	$1^6 + 6^1$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^7 + 7^1$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$

Exercise 2. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 4 in natural numbers:

		$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$

2.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 5. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 given by

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

Example 6. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 given in Example 5 is given by

		$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
	$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^7 + 7^1$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$1^6 + 6^1$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$

Exercise 3. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 5 in natural numbers:

		$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$
	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$
$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$
$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$
$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$
$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$
	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$

2.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 7. Let's consider a magic square of order 6 given by

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

Example 8. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 6 given in Example 7 is given by

						$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	$1^7 + 7^1$	$1^1 + 3^3$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$1^6 + 6^1$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$

Exercise 4. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 6 in natural numbers:

						$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$
$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$

2.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 9. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 is given by

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

Example 10. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 given in Example 9 is given by

		$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
	$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^6 + 6^1$	$1^7 + 7^1$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	$1^1 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$
	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$

Exercise 5. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 7 in natural numbers:

		$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$

2.6 Magic Square of Order 8

Example 11. Let's consider a **pan magic square** of order 8 is given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Example 12. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal magic square of order 8** given in Example 11 is given by

$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^2 + 2^1$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$
$1^7 + 7^1$	$-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$1^6 + 6^1$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$
$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$
$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$
$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 3^3$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$
$1^5 + 5^1$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$
$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$
$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 8 is given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2^2 + 4^4$$

In this case the blocks of order 4 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := -1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 6^3$$

Exercise 6. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 8 in natural numbers:

$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$
$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
$-1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$-1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	31
$2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$1^1 + 3^3$
$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$
$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
$1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 9^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$2^4 + 4^2$
$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 8 is given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$$

In this case the blocks of order 4 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$$

2.7 Magic Square of Order 9

Example 13. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
369	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Example 14. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal magic square of order 9** given in Example 13 is given by

$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	$-1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^1 + 3^3$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$
$-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^7 + 7^1$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$-1^2 + 2^1$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$2^7 - 7^2$
$1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$-1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$-1^3 + 3^1$
$1^2 + 2^1$	$-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^6 + 6^1$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$
$1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$
$2^3 + 3^2$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$
$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 9 is given by

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3$$

In this case, the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares (sum of only rows and columns) with equal **semi-magic** sums.

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$$

Exercise 7. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4 write the following magic square of order 9 in natural numbers:

$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$
$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$
$-1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 9^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$
$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 7^1$	$1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$
$-1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$
$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$
$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$
$1^1 + 3^3$	$2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$
$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 9 is given by

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1$$

In this case, the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares (sum of only rows and columns) with equal **semi-magic** sums.

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$$

2.8 Magic Squares of Order 10

Example 15. Let's consider a magic square of order 10 is given by

										505
1	80	65	97	39	22	48	86	53	14	505
98	12	9	66	90	74	55	33	41	27	505
47	81	23	79	16	35	94	60	62	8	505
70	57	88	34	2	91	29	15	76	43	505
84	99	52	11	45	68	73	7	30	36	505
13	38	44	10	77	56	82	21	95	69	505
75	46	40	83	28	19	67	92	4	51	505
59	24	96	42	61	3	20	78	37	85	505
26	5	17	58	93	50	31	64	89	72	505
32	63	71	25	54	87	6	49	18	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 16. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 10 given in Example 15 is given by

$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$
$-1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$1^8 + 8^1$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$
$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^7 + 7^1$
$-1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$
$1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$-1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$1^6 + 6^1$	$1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$
$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^9 + 9^1$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$-1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$-1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$
$1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^1 + 3^3$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$
$1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	$-1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$
$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^1 + 2^2$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 7^1$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$
$2^4 + 4^2$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 9^2$	$1^5 + 5^1$	$-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$2^6 + 6^2$

In this case the **magic sum** of magic square of order 10 is given by

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^1$$

2.9 Block-Bordered Magic Squares

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 based on magic squares of order 8 given in Examples 11 and 12.

Example 17. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by*

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

In this case the 4 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 202$. The magic square of order 8 is with magic sums $S_{8 \times 8} := 404$. The magic sum of order 10 is $S_{10 \times 10} := 505$.

Example 18. Based on **permutable base-power** representations given in Appendix 4, the **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 given in Example ?? is given by

$1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^3 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$1^3 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$1^3 + 3^1$	$-1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$-1^3 + 3^1$	$-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$
$-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$-1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$-1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$
$2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	$1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$
$-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$-1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$-2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$2^2 + 3^3$	$1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$
$1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^1 + 3^3$	$1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	$1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$1^1 + 2^2$
$-1^2 + 2^1$	$1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$2^5 + 5^2$	$-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	$-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$1^1 + 3^3$	$-1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$2^6 + 6^2$
$-1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 7^1$	$1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	$1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$1^7 + 7^1$
$1^5 + 6^1$	$-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	$1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$2^4 + 4^2$	$-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$
$-1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	$1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	$-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$1^5 + 5^1$
$1^8 + 8^1$	$1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$2^3 + 3^2$	$-1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 9^2$	$1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$1^2 + 2^1$	$-1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$1^9 + 9^1$

In this case the 4 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. Below are magic sums:

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} = 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^1$$

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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4 Appendix: Permutable Power-Base Digits Representations

Within the magic squares we have used total 1 to 100 numbers for the magic squares of orders 3 to 10. The magic sums vary according to each magic square. Any way the maximum number is 505. Below are representations of numbers from 1 to 1000 in terms **permutable power-base digits**. These representations are given in two two different ways one starting with 0 and another starting with 1. In some cases, we have small length representations when we start from 0. Any how, the whole work given in Section 1 is starting from 1. More details can be seen in author's work [1, 5, 6].

$0 := -0^0 + 1^1$	$= -2^4 + 4^2$	$15 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$
$1 := 0^1 + 1^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^1$	$16 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$
$2 := 0^0 + 1^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^1$	$17 := 2^3 + 3^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^2$
$3 := -0^0 + 2^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^1$	$18 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$
$4 := 1^3 + 3^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^1$	$19 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$
$5 := 0^0 + 2^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^2$	$20 := -1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	$= -1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$
$6 := 1^5 + 5^1$	$= 1^5 + 5^1$	$21 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$
$7 := 1^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^6 + 6^1$	$22 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$
$8 := 1^7 + 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 7^1$	$23 := -2^2 + 3^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^3$
$9 := 1^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 8^1$	$24 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$
$10 := 1^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 9^1$	$25 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$
$11 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	$26 := -0^0 + 3^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^3$
$12 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	$27 := -0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$
$13 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	$28 := 0^0 + 3^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^3$
$14 := 1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	$29 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$

30 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	54 := $0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$
31 := $2^2 + 3^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^3$	55 := $2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$
32 := $2^4 + 4^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^2$	56 := $-0^0 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$
33 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 4^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$	57 := $2^5 + 5^2$	$= 2^5 + 5^2$
34 := $1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	58 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 5^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$
35 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 6^2$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$	59 := $1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$
36 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	60 := $-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$= -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$
37 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 6^2$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	61 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$
38 := $1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	62 := $1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	$= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$
39 := $1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	63 := $0^2 + 2^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$
40 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	64 := $-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	$= -2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$
41 := $0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 - 6^3$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$	65 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
42 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	66 := $-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
43 := $0^6 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 6^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$	67 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$
44 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$	68 := $1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$
45 := $-0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	69 := $-1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$
46 := $-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	70 := $-0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$
47 := $-0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$	71 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$
48 := $0^7 - 2^0 + 7^2$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	72 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$
49 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 7^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	73 := $2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$
50 := $0^7 + 2^0 + 7^2$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	74 := $0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$
51 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 7^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	75 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$
52 := $1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	76 := $-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$
53 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$	77 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$

78 := $-0^0 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	102 := $-2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$= -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$
79 := $2^7 - 7^2$	$= 2^7 - 7^2$	103 := $0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$
80 := $0^0 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	104 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$
81 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	105 := $2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$
82 := $0^9 + 2^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	106 := $2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$
83 := $0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	107 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$
84 := $1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	108 := $1^7 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$
85 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	109 := $0^9 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$
86 := $1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	110 := $1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
87 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 9^2$	111 := $0^4 + 2^7 - 4^2 - 7^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
88 := $-0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	112 := $3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$	$= 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$
89 := $2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	113 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$
90 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	114 := $-2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$
91 := $0^6 + 2^7 - 6^2 - 7^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	115 := $0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$
92 := $0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 5^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	116 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$
93 := $0^6 + 2^7 - 6^2 + 7^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 7^1$	117 := $-0^0 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$
94 := $0^2 - 2^5 + 3^0 + 5^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	118 := $3^5 - 5^3$	$= 3^5 - 5^3$
95 := $0^8 + 2^5 - 5^0 + 8^2$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	119 := $0^0 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$
96 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	120 := $-1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$
97 := $0^8 + 2^5 + 5^0 + 8^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	121 := $-1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$
98 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	122 := $1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$
99 := $-0^0 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	123 := $1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$
100 := $2^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^6 + 6^2$	124 := $0^5 - 3^0 + 5^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 7^1$
101 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	125 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3$

$$\begin{aligned}
 126 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 5^3 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 6^2 \\
 127 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 - 7^0 &= -1^5 + 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 128 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^0 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 6^2 \\
 129 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 7^0 &= 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 130 &:= 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^0 &= -1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 6^3 \\
 131 &:= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 132 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^4 - 5^3 &= 1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 6^3 \\
 133 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 134 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 \\
 135 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 \\
 136 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 \\
 137 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 \\
 138 &:= -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 &= -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
 139 &:= 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 &= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
 140 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 \\
 141 &:= -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 \\
 142 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 \\
 143 &:= -2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3 &= -2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3 \\
 144 &:= -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 \\
 145 &:= 3^4 + 4^3 &= 3^4 + 4^3 \\
 146 &:= 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 \\
 147 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^3 \\
 148 &:= 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^3 &= 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^3 \\
 149 &:= 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 &= 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 150 &:= 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^2 &= 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^2 \\
 151 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 - 3^0 + 6^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^2 \\
 152 &:= 0^5 + 2^7 + 5^2 - 7^0 &= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 \\
 153 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 6^3 &= -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 154 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^0 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 6^3 \\
 155 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2 &= 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 156 &:= -2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2 &= -2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2 \\
 157 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2 \\
 158 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 5^3 &= 1^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
 159 &:= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3 \\
 160 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 \\
 161 &:= -2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 &= -2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 \\
 162 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 \\
 163 &:= 0^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 - 7^0 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^1 \\
 164 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2 \\
 165 &:= 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2 &= 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2 \\
 166 &:= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 &= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 \\
 167 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 \\
 168 &:= -1^8 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
 169 &:= 1^9 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 9^1 &= 1^9 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 9^1 \\
 170 &:= -1^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 &= -1^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
 171 &:= -1^5 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^2 &= -1^5 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^2 \\
 172 &:= -1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 &= -1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 \\
 173 &:= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2 &= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2
 \end{aligned}$$

174 := $0^9 - 2^0 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2$	198 := $-0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$
175 := $2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	199 := $-2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$	$= -2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$
176 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 7^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 7^2$	200 := $0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$
177 := $2^7 + 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 7^2$	201 := $-0^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^7 - 7^1 + 9^2$
178 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 7^2$	202 := $4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$	$= 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$
179 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 7^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2$	203 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$
180 := $0^4 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2$	204 := $2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$
181 := $1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2$	205 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$
182 := $1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2$	206 := $-2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	$= -2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$
183 := $1^5 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^2$	207 := $0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$
184 := $1^6 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 7^2$	$= 1^6 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 7^2$	208 := $-2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$= -2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3$
185 := $-1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	209 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$
186 := $-1^5 + 2^8 - 5^1 - 8^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 - 5^1 - 8^2$	210 := $-2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$
187 := $1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	211 := $-0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$
188 := $-1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 8^2$	212 := $-1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	$= -1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$
189 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$	213 := $-0^0 + 1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$
190 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 8^2$	214 := $1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$
191 := $-0^0 + 2^8 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$	215 := $0^6 - 3^0 + 6^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$
192 := $2^8 - 8^2$	$= 2^8 - 8^2$	216 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^0 + 6^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^3$
193 := $0^0 + 2^8 - 8^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$	217 := $0^6 + 3^0 + 6^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$
194 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 8^2$	218 := $-1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$
195 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$	219 := $2^8 + 3^3 - 8^2$	$= 2^8 + 3^3 - 8^2$
196 := $1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 8^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 8^2$	220 := $1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$
197 := $-1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	221 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$

222 := $-1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^3$	= $-1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^3$	246 := $-1^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	= $-1^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$
223 := $-0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	247 := $-1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$
224 := $-2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $-2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	248 := $-1^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	= $-1^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$
225 := $-2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $-2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	249 := $1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$	= $1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$
226 := $2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	= $2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	250 := $-1^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$	= $-1^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$
227 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	251 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 4^4$	= $-1^1 - 2^2 + 4^4$
228 := $-0^0 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $-1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	252 := $-2^2 + 4^4$	= $-2^2 + 4^4$
229 := $-3^3 + 4^4$	= $-3^3 + 4^4$	253 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 4^4$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 4^4$
230 := $0^0 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	254 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^4$	= $1^3 - 3^1 + 4^4$
231 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	255 := $-0^0 + 4^4$	= $-1^1 + 4^4$
232 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	256 := $-0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4$	= $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4$
233 := $2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	257 := $0^0 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 4^4$
234 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	258 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4$	= $-1^3 + 3^1 + 4^4$
235 := $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 5^1$	= $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 5^1$	259 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 4^4$	= $1^2 + 2^1 + 4^4$
236 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^1$	260 := $2^2 + 4^4$	= $2^2 + 4^4$
237 := $-1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	= $-1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	261 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 2^2 + 4^4$
238 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4$	262 := $1^5 + 4^4 + 5^1$	= $1^5 + 4^4 + 5^1$
239 := $1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	= $1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	263 := $-1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$
240 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	= $1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4$	264 := $1^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$	= $1^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$
241 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^0$	= $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^1$	265 := $1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$	= $1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$
242 := $0^3 + 3^5 - 5^0$	= $-1^9 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 9^1$	266 := $1^9 + 4^4 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 4^4 + 9^1$
243 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	= $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^1$	267 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^4 + 9^1$	= $1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^2$
244 := $0^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	= $-1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^4$	268 := $0^8 - 3^5 - 5^0 + 8^3$	= $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^4$
245 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	= $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^1$	269 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^2$

270 := $-0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	= $-1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	294 := $0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2$	= $1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2$
271 := $2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	= $2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	295 := $1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^2$	= $1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^2$
272 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	= $-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	296 := $0^6 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 6^3$	= $-1^7 + 2^8 + 7^2 - 8^1$
273 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	= $2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	297 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 7^2 - 8^1$	= $1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1$
274 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	298 := $0^6 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 6^3$	= $1^7 + 2^8 + 7^2 - 8^1$
275 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	299 := $-1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$	= $-1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$
276 := $2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	= $2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	300 := $-1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^3$	= $-1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^3$
277 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	= $1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	301 := $1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$	= $1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$
278 := $-3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4$	= $-3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4$	302 := $-1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	= $-1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
279 := $-2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $-2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	303 := $1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1$	= $1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1$
280 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	304 := $0^7 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2$	= $1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
281 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^4 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1$	305 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2$	= $-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2$
282 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $-1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	306 := $0^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2$	= $-1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
283 := $3^3 + 4^4$	= $3^3 + 4^4$	307 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2$	= $1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2$
284 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	308 := $0^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^0$	= $1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$
285 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	309 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2$	= $-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2$
286 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	310 := $-1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 - 9^1$	= $-1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 - 9^1$
287 := $2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	311 := $-1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1$	= $-1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1$
288 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	= $1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	312 := $-0^0 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$
289 := $2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	= $2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	313 := $2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	= $2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$
290 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	= $1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	314 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	= $1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$
291 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 6^2$	= $1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^2$	315 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	= $1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
292 := $-0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2$	= $1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 8^1$	316 := $-1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 8^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 8^2$
293 := $2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2$	= $2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2$	317 := $-0^0 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 8^2$

318 := $-3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	342 := $0^7 - 3^0 + 7^3$	= $1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 6^1$
319 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 8^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^8 + 8^2$	343 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 3^0 + 7^3$	= $1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3$
320 := $2^8 + 8^2$	= $2^8 + 8^2$	344 := $0^7 + 3^0 + 7^3$	= $-1^9 + 2^8 + 8^1 + 9^2$
321 := $0^0 + 2^8 + 8^2$	= $1^1 + 2^8 + 8^2$	345 := $-1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$
322 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 8^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 8^2$	346 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 8^2$
323 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 8^2$	= $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 8^2$	347 := $1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$	= $1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$
324 := $-0^0 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4$	= $1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 8^2$	348 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$	= $1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 8^2$
325 := $-4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4$	= $-4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4$	349 := $-1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3$
326 := $0^0 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4$	= $1^5 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 8^2$	350 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3$	= $1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 8^2$
327 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	= $1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	351 := $0^7 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3$
328 := $1^7 + 2^8 + 7^1 + 8^2$	= $1^7 + 2^8 + 7^1 + 8^2$	352 := $-2^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^2$	= $-2^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^2$
329 := $2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^2$	= $2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^2$	353 := $0^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 7^3$
330 := $1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 9^1$	354 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^1$
331 := $-1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 7^3$	355 := $-0^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$	= $1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 7^3$
332 := $3^6 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 6^4$	= $3^6 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 6^4$	356 := $2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$	= $2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$
333 := $0^7 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 7^3$	= $1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 7^3$	357 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$	= $1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$
334 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2$	358 := $-1^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $-1^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1$
335 := $2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2$	= $2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2$	359 := $-1^8 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 8^1$	= $-1^8 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 8^1$
336 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2$	= $1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2$	360 := $-1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1$	= $-1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1$
337 := $2^9 - 4^4 + 9^2$	= $2^9 - 4^4 + 9^2$	361 := $-1^6 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 6^1$	= $-1^6 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 6^1$
338 := $-0^0 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^9 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 9^2$	362 := $1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1$	= $1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1$
339 := $-1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	363 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$
340 := $-0^0 + 1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	= $1^9 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 9^2$	364 := $-2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	= $-2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$
341 := $1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	= $1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	365 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$

366 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^3$	390 := $-1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$
367 := $-0^0 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3$	391 := $-1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3$
368 := $3^5 + 5^3$	$= 3^5 + 5^3$	392 := $1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$
369 := $0^0 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3$	393 := $1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3$	$= 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3$
370 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3$	394 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$
371 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^3$	395 := $-2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$
372 := $2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	396 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$
373 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3$	397 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$
374 := $3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3$	$= 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3$	398 := $-0^0 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$
375 := $0^0 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3$	399 := $4^5 - 5^4$	$= 4^5 - 5^4$
376 := $-1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	400 := $0^0 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$
377 := $-1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	401 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$
378 := $1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	402 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^4$
379 := $1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	403 := $2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$
380 := $0^5 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2$	404 := $2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2$
381 := $0^3 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4$	$= 1^7 + 3^6 - 6^1 - 7^3$	405 := $0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2$
382 := $0^5 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	406 := $1^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 6^1$	$= 1^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 6^1$
383 := $0^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^0$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	407 := $1^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^1$
384 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^2$	408 := $1^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1$
385 := $0^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^0$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	409 := $1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1$
386 := $0^1 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2$	410 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$
387 := $0^7 + 3^6 + 6^0 - 7^3$	$= 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	411 := $0^8 - 2^6 - 3^0 - 6^2 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$
388 := $0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2$	412 := $0^2 + 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$
389 := $-1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1$	413 := $-0^0 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2$

414 := $2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2$	438 := $1^6 + 2^9 + 6^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^1 - 9^2$
415 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3$	439 := $1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 - 9^2$
416 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4$	440 := $1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 - 9^2$
417 := $-1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	441 := $0^0 + 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
418 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3$	442 := $-2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
419 := $-1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3$	443 := $0^0 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
420 := $-2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3$	444 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 6^2$
421 := $1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3$	445 := $-0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
422 := $0^4 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^8 + 2^9 - 8^1 - 9^2$	446 := $-3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
423 := $0^7 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^1 - 9^2$	447 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2$
424 := $0^4 - 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^1 - 9^2$	448 := $2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2$	$= 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2$
425 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -1^5 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$	449 := $0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2$
426 := $3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4$	450 := $2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
427 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 9^2$	451 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4$
428 := $1^4 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 9^2$	452 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$
429 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 9^2$	453 := $-1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$
430 := $-0^0 + 2^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 - 9^2$	454 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3$
431 := $2^9 - 9^2$	$= 2^9 - 9^2$	455 := $1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$
432 := $0^0 + 2^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 - 9^2$	456 := $-1^8 + 2^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^8 + 2^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$
433 := $2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2$	457 := $-0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2$
434 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2$	458 := $2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2$
435 := $1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 9^2$	459 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2$
436 := $1^4 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$	460 := $0^6 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 6^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 7^2$
437 := $1^5 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 9^2$	461 := $-0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$

462 := $2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	= $2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	486 := $0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^0$	= $-1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^1$
463 := $0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	= $1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	487 := $0^9 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^3$	= $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$
464 := $0^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 + 9^0$	= $-2^9 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^3$	488 := $0^5 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 9^0$	= $1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^1$
465 := $1^6 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 6^3$	= $1^6 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 6^3$	489 := $0^0 + 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^1$	= $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$
466 := $-1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1$	= $-1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1$	490 := $-1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
467 := $-1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	491 := $-0^0 + 1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	= $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$
468 := $1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1$	= $1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1$	492 := $1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	= $1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
469 := $1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	= $1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$	493 := $-1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1$
470 := $0^2 + 2^7 - 3^0 + 7^3$	= $1^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$	494 := $-0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1$	= $1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3$
471 := $0^6 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 6^3$	= $-1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 + 9^1$	495 := $0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^0$	= $1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1$
472 := $0^2 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 7^3$	= $1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$	496 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1$	= $1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 - 6^3$
473 := $0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 6^3$	= $-1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$	497 := $0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^0$	= $1^5 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$
474 := $0^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^0$	= $-1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$	498 := $0^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^0$	= $2^6 + 3^5 - 5^2 + 6^3$
475 := $0^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^0$	= $1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^3$	499 := $-2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4$	= $-2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4$
476 := $1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$	= $1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$	500 := $0^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^0$	= $-1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 8^3$
477 := $0^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 + 9^0$	= $1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^1$	501 := $-0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1$	= $-2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^2$
478 := $-1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^1$	= $-1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^1$	502 := $-1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1$
479 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $-1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	503 := $-3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4$	= $-3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4$
480 := $2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	504 := $1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1$	= $1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1$
481 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	= $1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	505 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1$	= $1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^1$
482 := $1^9 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	= $1^9 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	506 := $1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 8^3$	= $1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 8^3$
483 := $-2^7 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 7^3$	= $-2^7 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 7^3$	507 := $-0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3$	= $-1^5 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3$
484 := $0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^0$	= $-1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 + 9^1$	508 := $-1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3$	= $-1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3$
485 := $0^9 - 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^3$	= $-2^9 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 9^3$	509 := $-2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3$	= $-2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3$

510 := $1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3$	534 := $0^8 + 2^5 - 3^2 - 5^0 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$
511 := $0^2 + 2^9 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^1$	535 := $-0^0 - 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 7^3$
512 := $-0^0 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3$	536 := $0^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^1$
513 := $3^6 - 6^3$	$= 3^6 - 6^3$	537 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4$
514 := $0^0 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3$	538 := $0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^1$
515 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	539 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4$
516 := $1^8 + 3^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^8 + 3^1 + 8^3$	540 := $0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 - 9^1$
517 := $2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3$	541 := $0^1 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^3$
518 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3$	542 := $-0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4$
519 := $-0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^1$	543 := $-2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4$	$= -2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4$
520 := $-1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	544 := $-0^0 - 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3$
521 := $-0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^1$	545 := $-1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^1$
522 := $1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	546 := $3^6 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3$	$= 3^6 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3$
523 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^6 - 6^3 + 9^1$	547 := $0^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^1$
524 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 8^3$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 8^3$	548 := $2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3$
525 := $0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 8^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	549 := $0^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^1$
526 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3$	550 := $-2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$	$= -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$
527 := $0^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 9^1$	551 := $-1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$
528 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3$	552 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4$
529 := $0^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1$	553 := $1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$
530 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^3$	554 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4$
531 := $1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1$	555 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4$
532 := $2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	556 := $-1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$
533 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	557 := $-1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$

558 := $1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	= $1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	582 := $1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3$	= $1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3$
559 := $1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$	583 := $-0^0 - 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 + 9^1$	= $1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$
560 := $0^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^0$	= $2^8 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 8^2$	584 := $-1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 + 9^1$	= $-1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 + 9^1$
561 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^0$	= $1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$	585 := $0^7 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 + 2^9 - 7^1 + 9^2$
562 := $0^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^0$	= $-1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^4$	586 := $-1^6 + 2^9 - 6^1 + 9^2$	= $-1^6 + 2^9 - 6^1 + 9^2$
563 := $-1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4$	587 := $0^7 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 7^3$	= $-1^5 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 9^2$
564 := $1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^4$	= $1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^4$	588 := $-1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$
565 := $-0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2$	589 := $-1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^2$
566 := $2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2$	= $2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2$	590 := $1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$
567 := $0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2$	= $1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2$	591 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^2$
568 := $0^3 - 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4$	= $1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 - 9^1$	592 := $-0^0 + 2^9 + 9^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^9 + 9^2$
569 := $-1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	= $-1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	593 := $2^9 + 9^2$	= $2^9 + 9^2$
570 := $-1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	= $-1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	594 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 9^2$	= $1^1 + 2^9 + 9^2$
571 := $1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	= $1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	595 := $-3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3$	= $-3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3$
572 := $1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	= $1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	596 := $0^0 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3$	= $-1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$
573 := $0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	= $1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4$	597 := $0^5 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4$	= $1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^2$
574 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	598 := $0^7 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 7^3$	= $1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$
575 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	599 := $0^5 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 9^2$
576 := $2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	= $2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	600 := $0^7 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 7^3$	= $1^6 + 2^9 + 6^1 + 9^2$
577 := $-2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	601 := $1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 + 9^2$	= $1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 + 9^2$
578 := $0^0 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	602 := $1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 + 9^2$	= $1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 + 9^2$
579 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$	603 := $0^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^0$	= $1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$
580 := $-1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3$	604 := $-2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$
581 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$	605 := $0^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^0$	= $-1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$

606 := $-1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$	630 := $1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$
607 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	631 := $-3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4$	= $-3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4$
608 := $-0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	632 := $0^0 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4$	= $-1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$
609 := $-2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	633 := $-0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$
610 := $0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	634 := $1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$
611 := $1^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1$	= $1^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1$	635 := $2^2 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4$	= $2^2 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4$
612 := $1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$	636 := $-2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$
613 := $-2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^2$	= $-2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^2$	637 := $-0^0 - 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$
614 := $2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$	638 := $-1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$
615 := $-0^0 - 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$	639 := $-0^0 + 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$
616 := $-1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	640 := $0^5 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$
617 := $-0^0 + 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$	641 := $2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$
618 := $1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	642 := $0^5 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$
619 := $-0^0 - 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^2$	643 := $-1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3$
620 := $-1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	644 := $1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$
621 := $-0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^2$	645 := $1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3$	= $1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3$
622 := $1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	646 := $2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4$
623 := $0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$	647 := $0^9 - 3^4 - 4^0 + 9^3$	= $-1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4$
624 := $0^5 - 4^0 + 5^4$	= $3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$	648 := $-2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$
625 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$	649 := $0^9 - 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3$	= $1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4$
626 := $0^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $1^5 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	650 := $0^0 + 1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 - 8^2$
627 := $0^1 + 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $-2^2 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4$	651 := $0^5 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4$	= $-1^9 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$
628 := $-1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	652 := $-1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$
629 := $-0^0 + 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $3^4 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5$	653 := $0^5 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $1^9 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$

654 := $1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4$	678 := $0^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 6^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 - 9^2$
655 := $-1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$	679 := $0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	= $1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$
656 := $0^2 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^4$	= $1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$	680 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0$	= $-1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2$
657 := $1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$	681 := $0^5 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$
658 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $-1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1$	682 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0$	= $1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2$
659 := $0^1 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$	683 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$
660 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	684 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$
661 := $-0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4$	685 := $-2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $-2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$
662 := $1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	686 := $0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$
663 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	= $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 5^4$	687 := $2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	= $2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$
664 := $0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0$	= $1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1$	688 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	= $1^1 + 2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$
665 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0$	= $-1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	689 := $3^6 - 4^4 + 6^3$	= $3^6 - 4^4 + 6^3$
666 := $0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0$	= $-2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	690 := $0^5 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2$
667 := $0^1 + 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0$	= $1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	691 := $-1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4$
668 := $2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4$	692 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2$
669 := $-0^0 - 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$	= $-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	693 := $1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4$	= $1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4$
670 := $-1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$	= $-1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$	694 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2$
671 := $2^8 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$	= $2^8 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$	695 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4$
672 := $-0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	696 := $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2$
673 := $2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	697 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4$
674 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	698 := $0^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^0$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2$
675 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	699 := $-2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4$	= $-2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4$
676 := $0^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^2$	= $1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$	700 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$
677 := $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	= $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4$	701 := $2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	= $2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$

$702 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2$	$726 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$703 := 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 8^3$	$= 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 8^3$	$727 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$
$704 := -3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 6^3$	$= -3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 6^3$	$728 := 0^3 + 3^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$705 := 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^3 - 8^2$	$= 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^3 - 8^2$	$729 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 9^3$
$706 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2$	$730 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$707 := 0^9 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^3$	$731 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3$
$708 := 3^7 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4$	$= 3^7 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4$	$732 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$709 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^9 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^3$	$733 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3$
$710 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 6^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^1$	$734 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$711 := 2^9 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$735 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 9^3$
$712 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$= 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$736 := 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$713 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$	$737 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 9^3$
$714 := -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$738 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$715 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$739 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 9^3$
$716 := 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$740 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$717 := -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$741 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 9^3$
$718 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$742 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$719 := 0^9 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$743 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1$
$720 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$744 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$
$721 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$745 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 8^3$
$722 := -1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$746 := 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2$
$723 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3$	$747 := 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 8^3$
$724 := 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1$	$748 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^1$
$725 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$	$749 := -1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3$	$= -1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3$

750 := $-0^0 + 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 = 1^4 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 8^3$	774 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2$
751 := $1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 = 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3$	775 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^2$
752 := $0^0 + 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2$	776 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3$
753 := $-2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 = -2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$	777 := $2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 = 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3$
754 := $0^8 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 8^3 = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2$	778 := $0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3$
755 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^1$	779 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^2$
756 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2$	780 := $0^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^2 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 8^3$
757 := $-2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2$	781 := $0^8 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^1$
758 := $0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2$	782 := $0^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^2 = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$
759 := $2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3 = 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3$	783 := $0^4 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^2 + 8^3 = 1^5 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 8^3$
760 := $0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3 = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3$	784 := $0^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 8^2 = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2$
761 := $1^8 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 8^3 = 1^8 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 8^3$	785 := $-0^0 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1$
762 := $-1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2$	786 := $-1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 = -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$
763 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^9 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^3$	787 := $-0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1$
764 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 6^2 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2$	788 := $1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 = 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$
765 := $-2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 = -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3$	789 := $3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^5 = 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^5$
766 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2$	790 := $0^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$
767 := $0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 8^3 = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1$	791 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3$
768 := $-0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2$	792 := $0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$
769 := $3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 = 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3$	793 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3$
770 := $0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 8^3$	794 := $0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$
771 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^5 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 8^3$	795 := $0^1 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3$
772 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2$	796 := $0^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$
773 := $2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 = 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2$	797 := $-0^0 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3$

798 := $-1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	= $-1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	822 := $2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
799 := $2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^2$	= $2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^2$	823 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
800 := $1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	= $1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	824 := $1^8 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^1$	= $1^8 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^1$
801 := $0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	825 := $0^9 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3$	= $1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3$
802 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	826 := $0^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 7^0$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$
803 := $-0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	827 := $0^9 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3$
804 := $3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	828 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$	= $1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$
805 := $0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	829 := $-0^0 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2$	= $1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3$
806 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $-1^6 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 8^3$	830 := $2^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2$	= $2^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2$
807 := $1^9 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3$	= $1^9 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3$	831 := $0^4 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^2$	= $-1^9 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 9^3$
808 := $2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	= $2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	832 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$	= $1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$
809 := $0^9 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 9^3$	= $1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	833 := $2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$	= $2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$
810 := $0^1 - 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2 + 9^3$	834 := $0^0 + 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$	= $1^1 + 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3$
811 := $0^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3$	= $1^9 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$	835 := $0^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4$
812 := $0^1 + 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$	836 := $2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4$	= $2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4$
813 := $-1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$	837 := $0^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^2$	= $1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4$
814 := $-2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $-2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	838 := $1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 7^3 - 9^1$	= $1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 7^3 - 9^1$
815 := $1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$	= $1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$	839 := $-2^8 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3$	= $-2^8 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3$
816 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	840 := $-1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$
817 := $-0^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $-1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	841 := $0^7 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^3$	= $-1^4 - 2^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^2$
818 := $-3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $-3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	842 := $1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$
819 := $0^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	843 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$
820 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $-1^5 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 8^2$	844 := $-2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	= $-2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$
821 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	845 := $2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$	= $2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
 846 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 \\
 847 &:= -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 = -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 \\
 848 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
 849 &:= 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 = 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
 850 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
 851 &:= -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
 852 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
 853 &:= 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 854 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
 855 &:= 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 856 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\
 857 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 858 &:= -2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = -2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
 859 &:= -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 = -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
 860 &:= 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 = 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 861 &:= 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 = 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
 862 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^6 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
 863 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 864 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
 865 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 866 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 = -2^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
 867 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 868 &:= 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 = 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
 869 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 870 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1 \\
 871 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 872 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1 \\
 873 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 874 &:= -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
 875 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 876 &:= -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 877 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 878 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
 879 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^0 = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
 880 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 881 &:= -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 882 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 883 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 884 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
 885 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 886 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 887 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 888 &:= -2^5 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 = -2^5 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 \\
 889 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
 890 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 891 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 892 &:= 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
 893 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 894 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 & 918 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 895 &:= -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 919 &:= -2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 = -2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 896 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 920 &:= 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^0 - 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 897 &:= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 921 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
 898 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 922 &:= 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
 899 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 923 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
 900 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -2^6 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^4 & 924 &:= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
 901 &:= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 925 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
 902 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^9 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2 + 9^3 & 926 &:= 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
 903 &:= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 927 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
 904 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^9 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2 + 9^3 & 928 &:= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
 905 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 929 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
 906 &:= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 930 &:= -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
 907 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 931 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
 908 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 = -2^7 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 & 932 &:= 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
 909 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 933 &:= 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
 910 &:= -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & 934 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 \\
 911 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 935 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 = -1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 \\
 912 &:= 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 6^3 = 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 6^3 & 936 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
 913 &:= -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 = -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 & 937 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 \\
 914 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 & 938 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 = 1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
 915 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & 939 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 \\
 916 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 & 940 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
 917 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 941 &:= -2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3
 \end{aligned}$$

942 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	966 := $-1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$
943 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $-1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	967 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	= $1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$
944 := $-0^0 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $-1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$	968 := $1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	= $1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$
945 := $3^6 + 6^3$	= $3^6 + 6^3$	969 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$
946 := $0^0 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$	970 := $0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^0$	= $-1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
947 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $-1^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	971 := $0^9 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^3$	= $1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$
948 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$	972 := $0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0$	= $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
949 := $2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	973 := $0^9 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^3$	= $2^9 - 3^5 - 5^2 + 9^3$
950 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	= $1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3$	974 := $-1^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4$
951 := $1^5 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3$	= $1^5 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3$	975 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$
952 := $-1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	= $-1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	976 := $-1^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
953 := $1^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^1$	= $1^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^1$	977 := $2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$	= $2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$
954 := $1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	= $1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	978 := $-1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	= $-1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
955 := $1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 9^1$	979 := $-0^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $-1^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
956 := $-2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	= $-2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	980 := $3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
957 := $2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	= $2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	981 := $0^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	= $1^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
958 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$	982 := $-0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
959 := $-0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	983 := $-2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	= $-2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
960 := $-2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	= $-2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	984 := $0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	= $1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
961 := $2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$	= $2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$	985 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	= $-1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
962 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^3$	= $-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$	986 := $0^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^0$	= $2^8 + 3^5 - 5^2 + 8^3$
963 := $-0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1$	= $-1^7 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 7^2$	987 := $-1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$	= $-1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$
964 := $-1^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1$	= $-1^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1$	988 := $2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	= $2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$
965 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	= $-1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	989 := $1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$	= $1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$

$$990 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1 = -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$$

$$991 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1$$

$$992 := 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1 = 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$$

$$993 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 = 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1$$

$$994 := 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 9^3 = 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 9^3$$

$$995 := 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 = 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$$

$$996 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^0 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$$

$$997 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$$

$$998 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2 = 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$$

$$999 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2 = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$$

$$1000 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$$